

Red Emitting DBR Laser Array with 0.1 nm Wavelength Spacing Defined by Direct Write Ebeam Lithography

O. Brox^a, J. Fricke^a, R.-S. Unger^a, A. Maaßdorf^a, A. Mogilatenko^a,
M. Beier^a, H. Christopher^a, A. Knigge^a, and H. Wenzel^a

^a Ferdinand-Braun-Institut (FBH), Berlin, Germany
e-mail: olaf.brox@fbh-berlin.de

We present a distributed Bragg reflector diode laser array (DBR array) designed for digital holography on technical and biological surfaces. Compared to DBR arrays developed earlier [1] we shift towards shorter wavelengths around 662 nm (i) for increased penetration depth into biological tissue and (ii) for better adjustment options of the holographical systems (visible light). Integration of optical gratings into edge emitting diode lasers is a prerequisite for holographic applications, because it stabilizes emission wavelengths and reduces linewidths. We apply high order surface gratings [2] and focus on their definition with ebeam lithography, since it allows flexible control of the periods for different vertical laser structures. Controlled but small wavelength differences are requested for digital holography to generate long synthetical wavelengths [3]. Here we test ebeam direct write lithography to realize 0.1 nm wavelength spacing between adjacent emitters. Since current and temperature influence the emission wavelengths of DBR lasers the wavelength spacing should be obtained at similar operation points of the individual emitters.

Figure 1 shows the fabricated DBR array. The array with a footprint of 3.5 x 0.8 mm² is mounted p-side up on C-mount and contains four 3.5 µm wide ridge waveguides (RW) for fundamental lateral mode operation. Each emitter consists of an active and a grating section with lengths of 2.0 mm and 1.0 mm, respectively. The 0.5 mm long area behind the grating sections serves as the fan-out for the p-metal contacts. For the definition of the surface gratings we apply a hard mask that is structured with ebeam (Vistec SB251) and ZEP resist before it is transferred to the surface of the 3-inch wafer [2]. The gratings have periods of 1029.43 nm, 1029.62 nm, 1029.84 nm and 1030.01 nm (10th grating order) and the width of the grating slits in the hard mask was adjusted to 200 nm. The depth of the slits influences the reflectivity of the grating. Based on simulations with a mode expansion tool the target depth of the grating slits in the vertical laser structure is 1.40 µm. We measured a depth of around 1.37 µm on a FIB-cut in the lateral center of the RW (Fig. 2) and conclude from simulations that the power reflectivity of the DBR gratings is in the range of 0.8. After manufacturing the gratings, a standard RW process was applied. For measurements the array was facet coated to provide power reflectivities of 0.3 and < 10⁻³ for the front and rear facet, respectively. Figure 3 summarizes the Light-Current-curves (L-I-curves) for single emitter operation. The threshold currents for all emitters are around 60 mA and at 150 mA pump current the optical power is above 70 mW. The optical spectra show single mode behavior with an optical side mode suppression of 60 dB (Fig. 4). Switching from single emitter to simultaneous operation of several emitters was investigated also and shows no significant changes in the optoelectronic performances. The peak wavelengths over pump current are summarized in Fig. 5. At a pump current of 130 mA the spectral distance of adjacent emitters is between 0.089 nm and 0.123 nm. The current range without DBR mode jumps is about 20 mA and allows 0.03 nm wide mode hop free tuning for further fine adjustment of the wavelength spacing.

In this study we successfully applied direct write ebeam lithography to fabricate a high-performance red emitting DBR array with a wavelength spacing around 0.1 nm. Dimensions and optoelectronic performances make the array an excellent light source for digital holographic systems.

- [1] O Brox et al 2015 Electronics Letters 51, 17 DOI 10.1049/el.2015.2030
- [2] J Fricke et al 2012 Semicond. Sci. Technol. 27 055009 DOI 10.1088/0268-1242/27/5/055009
- [3] A Gröger et al 2023 J. Eur. Opt. Society-Rapid Publ., 19, 25 DOI 10.1051/jeos/2023024

Fig. 1 DBR array with four RW emitters (spacing $127.5 \mu\text{m}$). Lengths are 2.0 and 1.0 mm for the active and the grating sections, respectively.

Fig. 2 Grating section: SEM of a FIB-cut in the lateral center of the $3.5 \mu\text{m}$ wide RW.

Fig. 3 L-I-curves of the four emitters of the DBR array.

Fig. 4 Optical spectra at pump a current of 130 mA.

Fig. 5 Measured peak wavelengths over pump current. Each emitter is pumped separately. All measurements at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.